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oHMint: Online Higher Mathematics for MINT Students
An Online Mathematics Course and Learning Platform

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INTRODUCTION

Over the last decades, digitalisation has become an increasingly important aspect of teaching and studying at university level. Online learning tools address this current spirit and offer opportunities that go well beyond the classical textbook: practically unlimited temporal and spatial flexibility while maintaining a high level of interaction with the learners are just two of these.

The project oHMint is an ongoing initiative with the goal of providing an online self-study course and learning platform for higher mathematics, aimed at all students of engineering degree programmes at German universities – an enhanced university course with all the advantages that a digital learning environment offers. Its kickoff is organized and funded through the Hamburg Open Online University, with the technical implementation being handled by integral-learning GmbH. The oHMint project was initiated by the OMB+ consortium, a group of 14 German universities offering an online mathematics bridging course for those interested in a STEM university degree programme. This bridging course is being used extensively at around 50 German institutions, and oHMint benefits significantly from the expertise gained through its development. Currently, one chapter of oHMint is being produced in a pilot project as a prototype for the future development of the entire course spanning four semesters. This serves as an opportunity to test the implementation of new didactical approaches for delivering content as well as innovative types of exercises, taking into account the specific needs of young people today when it comes to learning mathematics. The full oHMint course will provide freshmen and students of higher semesters with a modern way of transitioning smoothly from a high school level of knowledge in mathematics to a bachelor degree level. One of its unique characteristics is the broad support of the universities in the OMB+ consortium and user group, which is a promising base for a wide acceptance of oHMint throughout Germany.

This paper is structured as follows. Chapter 1 covers the background of oHMint, giving an overview of OMB+ and HOOU. Structure and content of the course are explained in chapter 2, while chapter 3 deals with didactical methods and innovative aspects of oHMint. Chapter 4 concludes and presents an outlook for the future.

1 BACKGROUND OF OHMINT

1.1 The Online Mathematics Bridging Course OMB+

The “Online Mathematik Brückenkurs Plus” (“Brückenkurs” translates to “Bridging Course”), short OMB+ is an online learning platform directed towards those interested in STEM degree programmes. It offers participants the means to repeat and complement high school mathematics and more precisely, the subject matters defined in the cosh catalogue [1]. Mathematically based in this catalogue, the OMB+ has been developed by a consortium of 14 German universities and the company integral-learning GmbH under the auspices of TU9, an alliance of nine big technical universities in Germany. It is a successor of the course OMB (see [2]), which had been created by the KTH Royal Institute of Technology in Stockholm and translated into German by a cooperation between several German universities. The OMB+ is text oriented, but includes a big amount of questions, interactive elements, videos and examples with standard solutions which can be uncovered step by step. Until now, around 50 German institutions (universities, the German Physical Society DPG and others) use and recommend the OMB+, which is also available in English. Supplementary chapters covering e.g. stochastics, complex numbers and formal logic have been added, further educational videos are in the making and the translation into Chinese is in progress. For more information see [3] and www.ombplus.de.

1.2 The Hamburg Open Online University (HOOU)

The [HOOU](http://www.hooou.de) is a joint initiative of six institutions of higher education in Hamburg: Universität Hamburg (UHH), Hamburg University of Applied Sciences (HAW), Hamburg University of Technology (TUHH), HafenCity University Hamburg (HCU), Hochschule für bildende Künste (HFBK) and the Hochschule für Musik und Theater (HFMT). It was founded by the Hamburger Senat (Senate of Hamburg) in 2015 as the educational branch of “Strategie Digitale Stadt” (Strategy Digital City), an initiative to bundle processes of digitalization within the city.

The HOOU has four guiding principles. First, a clear *focus on learners and collaboration*: the students are at the centre of all efforts concerning the development of study materials and learning scenarios. Second, *scientificity*: studying at HOOU is oriented towards academic learning and fosters the solving of problems. Third, *engaging new target groups*: the HOOU is open for everybody who is interested in the discussion of academic subject matters and not exclusively for students of the involved institutions. And finally, *openness*: the HOOU is oriented towards open education and facilitates the creation and distribution of open educational resources.

The production of the first chapter of oHMint is funded by the HOOU and running from November 2017 through December 2018.

2 STRUCTURE AND CONTENT OF OHMINT

2.1 Modularisation

The preliminary structure of the curriculum for the full oHMint course was designed by the OMB+ consortium. It spans four semesters and aims to cover all the mathematics typically taught in STEM studies at German universities. The curriculum was carefully structured, keeping in mind that different (types of) universities have different needs for their respective degree programmes. With oHMint, eventually available in German and English, we aim to create a course that consists of units which can be combined in various ways to cover these needs. The fact that a broad spectrum of institutions is represented in the OMB+ consortium justifies our hope that the final course will be widely accepted within the relevant community. This clearly distinguishes oHMint from existing higher mathematics online courses at German institutions.

There are three types of units in oHMint: *base units* cover standard content and are expected to be included in every higher mathematics course, regardless of the institution it is taught at. *Supplementary units* go deeper into the (theoretical) background of a base unit, and include more abstract views on base unit concepts as well as more involved parts. Finally, *optional units* exist for subjects that are not necessarily always part of a higher mathematics course, depending in particular on the study programme and/or institution. The idea is that lecturers will be able to choose and combine the units that are relevant for their classes to provide students with everything they need (but not more).

Parallel to the development of the content of oHMint, a data base is being created that keeps track of all the interconnections between mathematical concepts and results in the units and which will help to ensure the desired modularity of the course.

The units themselves are text-based and consist of lectures, exercises, trainings and final tests. They are supplemented by videos where important concepts or ideas are also shown. Each chapter starts with a motivation for the new mathematical concepts taught such that students develop a sense for the importance of the content they are supposed to learn. Moreover, many interactive elements are being implemented in oHMint, some are discussed in more detail below.

2.2 Scope of oHMint and ECTS

The full first-semester oHMint course consists of the following units:

- Three base units: numbers and functions, differential calculus, integral calculus.
- Four supplementary units: differential calculus, integral calculus, sequences, series.
- Eight optional units: continuity, determination of zeros, L'Hospital's rule, partial fraction decomposition, approximate integration, sequences, series, Fourier analysis.

The European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System is used at European institutions of higher education as well as in some non-European countries. Credit points measure the volume of learning based on workload and desired learning outcome. In Germany, one ECTS point is equivalent to 25-30 hours of studying.

An assignment between the content of the chapters of the oHMint first-semester course and ECTS points has been made by the oHMint working group. This has been done as follows: for five sets of lecture notes from different German universities, the number of pages covering the content of a single unit was set in proportion to the total number of pages. This ratio was then used to calculate the corresponding ECTS credits per unit as part of the ECTS credits for the whole class.

3 DIDACTICS AND INNOVATIVE ASPECTS OF OHMINT

3.1 Didactical Methods

Our guiding principles how higher mathematics should be taught are a spiral curriculum (after J. Bruner, see [4]) where relevant ideas and concepts are presented and evolved in repeated opportunities over the course, the development of intuitive understanding, awareness, and knowledge of mathematical thinking (see e.g. [5], [6]), and in general an application oriented approach within the engineering framework. Further for our project relevant approaches to teaching mathematics are described in [7]. On the other hand we have the constraints of an online platform with limited direct interaction, and students of engineering with an extrinsic motivation to study mathematics, even though with a high level of self-organization and determination that allows them to participate in a self-study course.

On the detailed level we follow the ideas of cognitive load theory [8] which focuses on the limited capacity of working memory of students. New ideas and concepts are introduced incrementally starting from the central issue and adding mathematical constraints as the subject evolves, always keeping the cognitive load small and focused. The formally exact representation is the result of this process and not as often a starting point of teaching, making the constructive process of mathematical knowledge visible to the students.

Our database of mathematical interconnections (see 2.1) supports the development of the spiral curriculum as examples and exercises are shared between the units and viewed from different perspectives, making the interconnections visible for students.

The distinction between intuitive thinking and correct formulation of mathematics as well as fostering the awareness of it is one of our main goals. New ideas are always associated with a purpose and followed by an interactive exercise allowing the students to evolve in a self-acting way and assess their progress continuously. Different types of exercises support the comprehension of ideas, the stabilization of acquired knowledge or the development of routine skills. Application-oriented exercises from science and engineering impart an understanding of the importance of the methods to the relevant application domains. Problem sets on different levels

of content that are automatically corrected allow the students to assess their growth of knowledge and prepare them for the exams.

3.2 Gamification

Gamification can be defined as the use of game design elements in non-game contexts, see [9]. This may take various forms, from gameful (rather than playful) interactions between different persons to the introduction of single player components aimed at increasing motivation and engagement in the individual. Since most engineering students are predominantly extrinsically motivated when it comes to learning mathematics, we develop a variety of such components for oHMint which create a new incentive for active participation in the course. It is the aim of the current pilot project to test several approaches and choose the most successful ones for implementation in the entire course which will subsequently be developed. A selection of these is described more detailed in the following.

- Badges: We are developing a system of badges that participants receive for completing certain tasks, such as finishing a chapter or unit, successfully solving problems or working on oHMint for x consecutive days. The positive effect of badges has been documented, see [10]. This will however be an optional element since not everyone likes to be “distracted” by such matters.
- Exercises in game form: For skills that require routine we are developing a gaming approach. The player is given a task such as “what is the derivative of the function $f(x)=\dots?$ ” and has a certain amount of time to answer it. If answered correctly, the player receives points and proceeds. There are different levels with harder exercises worth more points. After finishing the game, players have the option to enter their score into a high score list. We are also investigating the option of enabling players to compete against each other in a duel or small groups. However, the technical development of such a component lies beyond the scope of the current pilot project.
- We are also discussing the option of developing a game in the style of the well-known game show “Who wants to be a millionaire?”.

Developing and realizing these ideas we benefit from close interaction with the e-learning group at Universität Hamburg. Furthermore, we work with student helpers to get feedback from the target group of oHMint and include it directly into the development of the course. This enables us to create and design content in a way that is suitable for the needs of the next student generation.

3.3 What makes oHMint special?

Lecturers can design their own course by selecting content units depending on the degree programme or background (polytechnic/university). See 2.1, Modularisation.

We implement innovative types of exercises: audio files provide the opportunity to practice the transition between written and spoken mathematics – something that online courses often lack; in “reversed” exercises the students shall find flaws in a given line of arguments; in “drawing” exercises they are asked to sketch the graph of

a function with certain properties. Moreover, there is a large amount of quick checks, i.e. short questions or problems interspersed in the course where students can immediately check after the introduction of a new content if they understood it or not.

A group instructing mode will be available. In this way, professors can not only compile a course suitable for their needs but also follow the learning progress of their students in a gradebook overview. A flipped classroom version is also being created. And finally, a call centre run by integral-learning GmbH will be integrated into oHMint as it already is in the OMB+. This means that participants of oHMint can get help for mathematical questions from 10 am till 8 pm via internal chat, telephone, skype (telephone and chat) or internal forum as a free service.

4 RÉSUMÉ

4.1 Summary and a Look into the Future

As mentioned in 1.2, the production of the first oHMint base unit is funded by the HOOU. It is intended to serve as a sample for the production of the remaining units of the first semester course as well as for the second to fourth semester courses. The oHMint working group, currently a subgroup of the OMB+ consortium, plans to use this sample unit to create attention for the project and raise funding, as well as to convince other working groups to join the oHMint working group and/or produce a unit for oHMint themselves. After completion, each unit will be translated into English. A preliminary version of the base unit differential calculus will be put to the test in the winter term 2018/19 at HCU Hamburg as a flipped classroom version. This will provide valuable feedback from students of STEM degree programmes as well as from lecturers for the future development of oHMint.

Overall, we believe that oHMint poses an important step in the digitalisation of STEM education in Germany. The broad supporting base guiding its development ensures that it is tailor-made for the needs of lecturers and students alike, and its modular structure makes it suitable for all institutions.

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